

FAILURE AND RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF IN-SERVICE REPAIRED COMPOSITES

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Abstract

- Scarf-bonded technology has been widely used to joint or repair composite components in aircraft structures. Sometimes it is inevitable to perform repair directly on in-service components. In this paper, failure and reliability analysis of in-service repaired composites via scarf method were conducted.
- Tensile failure tests were firstly carried out on scarf-repaired composites of three different laminate thicknesses to elucidate the repair efficiency and failure modes. The failure strengths of each group are relatively close and the typical failure modes are similar. The dominated failure mode is cohesive failure of adhesive.
- In addition, a finite element model based on continuum damage model (CDM) and cohesive zone model (CZM) was established to predict the failure strength and damage mode. The can predict the failure strength and damage mode well. Based on the validated model, the effects of adhesive shear strength and mode II fracture toughness were discussed.
- At last, Weibull function was used to analyze the scatter in the experimental results and safe failure strengths at different reliability and confidence levels were estimated using time to first failure concept.

Test results

Thickness (mm)	Strength (MPa)	CV (%)
3.5	463.17	7.04
4.5	423.52	5.65
7	439.99	4.78

Numerical results

- The predicted failure load and damage mode agree well with the experimental results.
- Compared to mode II fracture toughness, the influence of adhesive shear strength is much obvious.

Reliability analysis

Weibull distribution

Time to first failure (TTFF) concept

Safe failure strength

$$F(x)|_{Weibull} = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right]$$

$$\sigma_{R\gamma} = \frac{\hat{\beta}}{S_M \cdot S_N \cdot S_R}$$

$$S_M = \left(\frac{1}{2m} X_\gamma^2(2m)\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha_n}}$$

$$S_N = \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)^{\frac{-1}{\alpha_n}}$$

$$S_R = \left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{R}\right)\right)^{\frac{-1}{\alpha_n}}$$

At various reliability ($\gamma=0.99$)

At various confidence levels ($R=0.99$)

